

Artificial Intelligence in Chemical Education and Curriculum

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Abstract:

Artificial Intelligence is imparting profound implications in professional practices such as scientific research particularly in the field of chemical science. Survey is conducted based on its effectiveness in the field of chemical education and related field. Key applications and problems are highlighted and addressed for its applications in education. Furthermore, this paper also introduces the AI related competencies into teaching learning framework tailored to its improved application in advanced chemical studies.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Chemical education, Curriculum

Introduction:

Artificial Intelligence is drastically reshaping chemistry education by facilitating the numerous AI- assisted tools for teaching, learning and research task. AI related competences becomes significant role in educating the researchers and educators to upgrade themselves through AI related framework. Many such tools are discussed in this paper to ensure scientific understanding through modernization. Not only in educational domain, but also in healthcare(3), and finance sector(16). AI system has designed to incorporate with the neural networks to collect data to better analysis it, enabling the advancement in scientific research and development of potent molecules. AI-powered tools such as AlphaFold , which is used to predict the protein structure, got noble prize by The Royal Swedish Academy of Science, in 2024. In addition to this, AI helps in creating model of molecules, particles interactions and material analysis (10,11).

AI improves educational environment for both researchers and educators to exchange knowledge through discussions and experiences that promotes peer to peer communication and brainstorming. It helps in catering comprehension through communication and proper execution. Various AI –

Assisted tools are listed below for learning chemistry through visual interface.(4,6)

- **Knewton** : It offers OER content, personalized learning environment and with application of adaptive technology to promote proficiency level in real time.(15)
- **Cognii** : It helps in developing critical thinking ability, conceptual understanding of particular topic.(21)
- **Blippar**: This application uses AI in integration with Augmented Reality to recognize images by providing immersive learning experience.(12)

DiKoLAN (Digital Kompetenzen für das Lehramt in den Naturwissenschaften) AI framework which aims to impart teacher education through structure oriented framework.(20,22) It uses AI simulation to deliver science lessons, developing curriculum and content creation. It helps in achieving AI Literacy among educator and teaching professionals). Particularly in the educational context, AI can be used for organizing training programs for teachers so as to develop a comprehensive curriculum, hands-on training sessions and practices collaboration and academic support with fellow colleagues or institution. (8)

Lists of AI- Driven tools for chemistry education are as follow:

AI tools	Application
ChemGPT	Helps in prediction of molecules and problem solving purpose
Chem copilot	Provide information of chemical processes and machine learning algorithm
Chemical.ai	Features for retrosynthesis, impurity predictions, efficient synthesis pathway
Deep Chem	For drug discovery, material science, checking toxicity
Graph2SMILES	Provide graph based data to predict organic synthetic pathway.
ChemIntelligence	Used for monitoring reaction optimization and pharmaceutical discovery
Julius AI	Graph based data creation and data analysis, modelling features.
Alphafold	Help to visualize 3D protein structure and sequence of amino acids , structural biology, analysing drug discovery
Hyperwrite Chemistry Assistant	Help to solve chemistry problem with detailed explanation.

AI in curriculum designing:

AI offers personalized learning environment for both educators as well as students. AI driven analytics provides latest updates on students progress, involvement and assigning assignments

so as to improve students performance based on the data collected. Various AI – driven tools provides best learning experiences in the field of education.(24,25).

AI tools	Applications
Brisk.ai	It has a feature that enables to design curriculum into engaging quizzes, activities, availability of resources such as textbook, Google Docs.
Student.ai	Help tutors to summarise complex pdf, YouTube videos to blogs, crafting research methodology with grammar checking features, simulated chat box for mock interviews, cover letter generator.
Anara.ai	Reliable tool for literature review
Gauthmath.ai	For assisting in complex calculations of physics, chemistry and maths
Claude.ai	Help in summarization of context, coding, reasoning, content creation and data analysis.
Notebooklm	Project planning, brainstorming, organizing information into actionable flashcards

Integration of AI powered tools with AR/VR:

3D lab Visualizations can be a promising opportunity if AI can be effectively integrated with Augmented Reality (AR). Such advancement just not only make the topic engaging and enriching but also improves understanding of complex reactions in real time analysis. In the latest studies, it was found that Virtual Reality (VR) simulation provides hand on learning environment for experiments without risking the hazards associated with particular experiments.(9)

Virtual Reality labs like **Labster** that simulate authentic laboratory environment for various reaction to carry on, help in understanding

the Biochemistry and complex reactions. Another tool such as **PhET** gives interactive simulated interface to identify the chemistry behind certain chemical change. **Chemcollective** application is used to visualize acid base reaction without comprising the hazards associated with physical laboratory while handling such chemicals. (9).

AI- driven technology provides dynamic and engaging environment for researchers and scholar to solve complex chemical reaction pathways through AI mimic laboratories.(19) AI simulation provides detailed information of certain complex parameters of testing such as temperature, concentration enabling to monitor the changes

occurs with the particular reactions. Indisputably, AI is leading when it comes to promotes virtual lab. (9)

Generative AI for Molecular Designing:

Generative AI explore various opportunities in Computational chemistry, thermal distribution of complex molecular systems and sampling structure.(13,14,17,24). Generative AI in integration with Computational chemistry provides information of potential energy surface (PES) by analysing the reaction mechanisms, Thermodynamic ensembles, finding degree of freedom by reducing dimension so as to find molecular structure for collective variable reaction co-ordinate for identifying the transition state, molecular simulation, latent variables. Generative AI enables to generate priors for simplifying model, loss function to identify the difference between generated sample and true data distribution so as to determine error and cross entropy, validation, regularization, embedding, attention mechanism enable to improve performance. (2,18,19)

AI Algorithm for Quantum Chemistry:

Deep neural networks have prominent feature in calculating high quantum level accuracy. It helps in solving electronics Schrödinger equation for ground and excited state by commanding through generative AI simulation. Generative AI impart immersive applications in physical science, models, structural and dynamical ensembles to solve complex chemical reaction and its statistical mechanism. Moreover, AI can also be used to solve underlying theories such as Boltzmann Statistical Mechanism, Marcus Theory for electron transfer calculation.(1,5)

The dominant role of Artificial Intelligence in Chemistry education promotes its usage in Chemistry related topics such as 3D visual lab,

AI has not gained any significance when it comes to retention of knowledge about a particular topic comparing it with traditional approach of learning. The data collected in the response are in

understanding complex interpretation and data analysis, in medicinal field while designing the new drugs and checking its effectiveness, it is important to integrate the AI in chemical science.(9)

The survey was designed to analysed and to get feedback of students specifically the Undergraduate and post graduate students related to AI in Chemistry education. The survey thoroughly facilitate the integration of AI in transforming chemical education. It is to be noted that previous studies showed that AI can be successfully used in molecular property predictions, drug discoveries, waste water treatment, retrosynthesis (Clark, 2023). The survey is aimed to addressed the comprehensive studies related to AI applications in education and to gain students prospective and convenience in the direction of modern technology. We received 35 responses from UG and PG students. The diversifying responses suggested its advantages and concern according to students prospective.

Does AI enhance your motivation to learn chemistry?

35 responses

Around 69% of the students have positive feedback on learning chemistry through the various application of AI such as ChatGPT, perplexity, meta AI, Gemini etc. Although many were not in support of its implementation in educational field.

partial favour of hike in Artificial Intelligence in modernization. Students still find traditional learning method as an adaptive or good approach for learning.

Reshaping and integrating the Artificial Intelligence with chemistry lab, students were asked to give their perception on lab Visualizations and analysing the complex chemical reaction through AI applications. Only 12% of students have agreed for the implementation of AI on the mentioned topic. Remaining responses are not sure about the consequences and its usage.

It is essential to know that how undergraduate and postgraduate students find AI applications as attractive and fascinating. The survey suggested the various features that are game changer for students' learning pace. When it comes to effective learning part, students find it useful and deliberately use to create the content that align with their topic on interest for their studies.

Additionally, students mostly use AI tools for Individualized learning. AI enables personalized content creation, assessment questions for real time analysis and provide deeper insights into real cutting edge learning analytics of particular topic. These help students to learn the particular topic of Chemistry in an accessible and flexible learning environment

Addressing the ethical concern associated with AI, students find some topic or concepts remains unclear while relying on AI for study purpose. Proper and exclusive explanations of the particular topics is still need of an hour. Moreover, privacy and data security is raising concern on its

inadequate consent of delivering data. The survey also suggested that AI also hindered the one's critical thinking ability. 54% of the students showed concern on gradual decreasing of critical thinking skill on solely relying on AI applications.

Students suggested on improvement in AI applications as

- Interactive Virtual Labs.
- Perfect images of concept
- 3D models, voice help, and quick quizzes to improve AI tools in chemistry
- Interactive simulations that allow students to experiment with different chemical

reactions and conditions in a virtual environment.

- Chemistry Problem Analyzer

Conclusions:

Artificial Intelligence provides best learning tools and compatible environment for learning. AI literacy, AI pedagogy, AI competences are becoming significant skill in learning chemistry through modern approach. Earlier, problems in theoretical chemistry part could not be solved

through traditional methods of solving. Although with rapid advancement in AI -Assisted tools, complex chemical equation can be solved effectively with accuracy. However there are certain drawback associated with overuse of AI. Data collected from survey suggested that over relying on AI tool is hindering the ability of critical

thinking. Privacy and data loss are the major ethical concern of Artificial Intelligence . Hence prerequisite knowledge and literacy of AI are necessary for its meaningful use.

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